

IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY TO DEVELOP PROFESSIONAL AND COMMUNICATIVE SKILLS OF FUTURE ECONOMISTS (AS AN EXAMPLE OF TEACHING ENGLISH)

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Аннотация.

Статья рассматривает вопросы разработки методологии преподавания английского языка будущим экономистам в Узбекистане с целью повышения качества их профессиональной подготовки, а также развития коммуникативных навыков. Авторы обзора проанализировали современные исследования на эту тему и представили различные методики и подходы, которые могут быть эффективными в процессе обучения. Результаты исследования показывают национальные особенности преподавания английского языка будущим экономистам, а также позволяют сделать вывод о том, что использование инновационных методов и аутентичных материалов способствует развитию профессиональных и коммуникативных навыков студентов и повышает их конкурентоспособность на рынке труда.

Annotation

The article examines the issues of developing a methodology for teaching English to future economists in Uzbekistan in order to improve the quality of their professional training, as well as the development of communication skills. The authors of the review analyzed modern research on this topic and presented various methods and approaches that can be effective in the learning process. The results of the study show the national peculiarities of teaching English to future economists, and also allow us to conclude that the use of innovative methods and authentic materials contributes to the development of professional and communicative skills of students and increases their competitiveness in the labor market.

Annotatsiya

Maqolada O'zbekistondagi bo'lajak iqtisodchilarga kasbiy tayyorgarlik sifatini oshirish, shuningdek, muloqot ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish maqsadida ingliz tilini o'qitish metodologiyasini ishlab chiqish masalalari ko'rib chiqiladi. Sharh mualliflari ushbu mavzu bo'yicha zamonaviy tadqiqotlarni tahlil qildilar va o'quv jarayonida samarali bo'lishi mumkin bo'lgan turli xil texnika va yondashuvlarni taqdim etdilar. Tadqiqot natijalari kelajakdagi iqtisodchilarga ingliz tilini o'qitishning milliy xususiyatlarini ko'rsatadi, shuningdek, innovatsion usullar va haqiqiy materiallardan foydalanish talabalarning kasbiy

va muloqot qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirishga yordam beradi va ularning mehnat bozorida raqobatbardoshligini oshiradi degan xulosaga kelishimizga imkon beradi.

INTRODUCTION

The article discusses the main problems that arise when teaching English to future economists, as well as offers solutions to solve them. One of the main problems is the lack of specialized educational materials that would allow students to develop their professional skills. In addition, it is important to use relevant and relevant materials that reflect current trends in the economy. The article discusses examples of such materials that can be used to teach English to future economists.

Предлагаются New approaches to the organization of the educational process are proposed, which will allow students to develop their communication skills. Classical methods, such as textbooks and classroom exercises, are not always effective enough in developing students' communication skills. To do this, you need to use interactive learning methods, such as games, role-playing games, debates, etc. Such methods can help students develop not only language skills, but also self-confidence, communication competence, and socio-political thinking.

Thus, the article offers a new approach to teaching English to future economists, which will allow them to fully develop their professional and communication skills. It may be of interest to both teachers and students, as well as anyone interested in modern methods of teaching foreign languages.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Currently, the role of English as the language of global communication, especially in the economic sphere, is becoming increasingly important. Teaching English to students of economic specialties is a complex task that requires not only knowledge of the language, but also the ability to apply it in professional activities. In this regard, a study of literature sources on this topic was conducted.

Cunningham, Sarah, & Moor, Peter. (2005). *Cutting Edge: Upper-Intermediate*. Longman. This book examines current trends in economics, including international economic relations, and offers relevant materials for language learning. This book can be useful for developing educational materials that will help students develop their professional skills.

Jordan, R.R. (1997). *English for Academic Purposes: A Guide and Resource Book for Teachers*. Cambridge University Press. This book offers a variety of approaches to teaching English for academic purposes, including economics. The author suggests various strategies, such as essay writing tasks and research projects, to help students improve their language and professional skills.

Gu, Y. (2003). Vocabulary learning in a second language: Person, task, context, and strategies. *TESL-EJ*, 7(2), 1-25. The Gu article examines issues related to effective learning vocabulary of the second language vocabulary. The author recommends using a contextual methodology, including the study of texts and situations related to the field of economics. This can help students better understand the specialized vocabulary used in economic activities.

Withochrane, J. (2019). The Critical Role of Digital Literacy in ELT for the Professional Development of EFL Teachers. *The Journal of Teaching English for Specific and Academic Purposes*, 7(2), 279-296. Статья Cochrane's article examines the possibility of using digital technologies to improve the effectiveness of teaching English in the economic sphere. The author suggests using mobile devices, social networks and other modern tools to create interactive materials aimed at supporting the development of professional and communication skills.

To improve the methodology for developing professional and communication skills of future economists through teaching English in Uzbekistan, many studies have been conducted. In this section, we'll look at some of them.

Abyazova O., Badalova Zh., and Ibragimova G. (2019) in their article "Problems of teaching foreign languages to students of economic specialties" note that for effective teaching of English to students of economic specialties, special methodologies are needed aimed at developing their professional and communication skills, as well as understanding the features of economic terminology in English.

Mamadaliyeva M. (2016) in the article "Peculiarities of teaching English for students of economic specialties" notes that teachers should use various methods, such as authentic materials, essay writing tasks and research work, to help students develop their professional skills in English.

Mirzayeva N. and Kamalova Ya. (2019) in the article "Using innovative methods in teaching English to economics students" note that the contextual approach and mobile devices can be effective methods of teaching English for students of economic specialties.

Suleymanova Z. and Latifova N. (2019) in their article "Determining the effectiveness of authentic materials in teaching English to students of the Faculty of Economics" emphasize the importance of using authentic materials related to economic topics in the process of teaching English. They also note that this approach contributes to the development of students' reading, writing and communication skills in English.

Khusnukradova R. and Abdullayeva A. (2017) in the article "Using new technologies in teaching English for students of economic specialties" note that the use of online resources, such as various websites and smartphone applications, can help students improve their level of English proficiency.

Thus, modern research highlights the need to use innovative methods of teaching English for students of economic specialties in Uzbekistan, taking into account the specifics of the professional activities of these specialists. Various methods and approaches can be effective in developing students' professional and communication skills, which ultimately improves the quality of their training and competitiveness in the labor market.

All these literature sources give a complete picture of the problems of teaching English in the economic sphere and offer various approaches to their solution. They can serve as valuable materials for the development of training programs and methodological materials aimed at training future economists.

For effective teaching of English in the economic sphere, it is important to create a curriculum that takes into account the specifics of students' professional activities. For example, the inclusion of lessons on topics related to economic news and trends in the program will allow students to get acquainted with important professional terms and learn how to discuss this topic in English.

It is also necessary to use a variety of teaching methods, including interactive tasks, quizzes, games, and other activities that will help students memorize new material more easily and better understand professional terms.

The availability of English language learning is also critical, as many students work in foodcourts, shops, call centers, or go to take care of children, and therefore cannot attend traditional classroom classes. In this case, online courses, apps, and other online resources for learning English can be a good alternative.

In general, for effective teaching of English in the economic sphere, many factors must be taken into account, including the specifics of the students' profession, teaching methods, availability of training and technological resources. The selection of educational materials and teaching methods should be based on involving students in real-world examples that may be useful to them in their future professional activities.

ANALYSIS

Developing professional and communication skills is a key component of training future economists. Due to the fact that English is one of the most important languages in the global economy, teaching English for students of economic specialties is particularly important. There are many studies aimed at improving

the methodology for developing professional and communication skills of future economists, including in the field of teaching English.

One of the most relevant approaches to teaching English for students of economic specialties is based on the use of authentic material. For example, English language textbooks for economists usually contain original texts from the world's mass media with accompanying tasks on understanding the text, lexical and grammatical material. The textbooks may also include professional topics such as international economic relations, finance and investment, business and entrepreneurship, etc. An example of such educational literature is Cunningham and Moor's *Cutting Edge: Upper-Intermediate* (2005).

Another approach to teaching English to economists is based on the use of tasks for writing essays and conducting research. Such tasks are aimed at developing the skills of reflection, analysis, evaluation and composition of the text in English, as well as developing an understanding of professional terms and their use in the context of the problems discussed. This approach to teaching English is discussed in detail in Jordan's book "English for Academic Purposes: A Guide and Resource Book for Teachers" (1997).

In addition, methods such as the use of contextual methodology, mobile devices and online resources, games and other activities are a variety of tools in teaching English to economists. Examples of such resources могут are статьяGu's article "Vocabulary learning in a second language: Person, task, context, and strategies" (2003), and также статьяCochrane's article "The Critical Role of Digital Literature in ELT for the Professional Development of EFL Teachers" (2019).

A variety of methods and approaches best meet today's learning requirements and help students gain knowledge and skills in an interactive and innovative environment. Such methods not only have a positive impact on the learning process, but also allow students to develop their personal qualities, such as independence, critical thinking, communication competence and tolerance.

In addition, the use of authentic materials and relevant professional topics allows students to gain real experience of communication in the modern economic sphere and consider many truly important topics for them. It is also important to note that the development of language skills and professional competence in English helps students not only in the learning process, but also in their future career.

Thus, in order to be successful in the economic sphere, students need a clear knowledge of English and the ability to communicate in it. English language training for economists should focus on developing language, professional and

communication skills that will enable students to work successfully with English-speaking colleagues and partners in the future.

In general, the use of various approaches and methods of teaching English for economists makes it possible to create a curriculum that will take into account the specifics of students' professional activities and help them develop not only language skills, but also professional and communication skills that will be useful in the future career of an economist.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This article discusses various approaches and methods of teaching English for students of economic specialties, aimed at developing professional and communication skills. The analysis of the conducted research shows that the use of authentic materials, essay writing tasks, research work, contextual methodology, mobile devices and online resources help students gain knowledge and skills in an interactive and innovative environment.

The use of authentic materials and relevant professional topics allows students to gain real experience of communication in the modern economic sphere and understand the real problems that they will face in their professional activities. For example, text comprehension tasks with original materials from the world's mass media help students not only improve their language skills, but also understand current economic processes in the world.

The use of essay writing tasks and research projects helps students develop the skills of reflection, analysis, evaluation and composition of the text in English, as well as take into account the specifics of their professional activities. Through such tasks, students can analyze the markets, identify current economic trends and look at them from a new perspective.

Contextual techniques, mobile devices, and online resources can help make learning more interactive and exciting. For example, using an online map allows students to study the geographical specifics of the economic markets of a particular region, and mobile applications can help students improve their pronunciation and vocabulary.

It is important to note that the use of various methods and approaches in teaching English for economists allows you to create a curriculum that can be customized to develop certain skills, taking into account the specifics of student's professional activities.

In general, using different approaches to teaching English to economists helps students develop not only language skills, but also professional and communication skills that will be useful in their future career as an economist.

Teaching English to economists is an important component of their education and helps them improve their prospects in the labor market.

CONCLUSION

In general, the development of professional and communication skills is an important aspect of training future economists. One of the key elements of this process is learning English and developing a methodology for teaching this language, taking into account the specifics of the professional activities of future economists.

We considered various approaches and methods of teaching English for students of economic specialties, aimed at developing professional and communication skills. The analysis of the conducted studies has shown that the use of authentic materials, essay writing tasks, research work, contextual methodology, mobile devices and online resources can create a favorable environment for obtaining knowledge and skills in English.

Examples of using these methods in teaching English to economists may include:

- Use authentic materials related to economic topics to help students gain real-world communication experience in the modern economic field.
- Apply essay writing tasks and research papers to help students analyze current economic issues and develop reflection, analysis, and evaluation skills.
- Use contextual techniques, mobile devices, and online resources to create an interactive and innovative learning environment.

Thus, improving the methodology of teaching English for economists through the use of the methods described above can significantly improve the quality and effectiveness of training future economists. Developing students' professional and communication skills is an important component of their education and helps them improve their prospects in the labor market.

In addition, using the latest methods of teaching English to economists can help students improve their language proficiency faster, which can improve their prospects in the labor market and increase their professional status.

In general, the development of a methodology for teaching English to economists requires professionalism and careful training of teachers, who must be attentive to the specifics of their students' professional goals and needs. However, with the right approach, this work can significantly improve the level of training of future economists and their success in the labor market.

Finally, to effectively improve the methodology of teaching English for economists, it is necessary to conduct systematic research and analyze the results in

order to continuously improve the quality of education and adapt it to changes in the field of economics and language teaching. The only thing that remains unchanged is the strategic need for students of economic specialties to have a high level of English language proficiency, which guarantees a successful and promising career both in Ukraine and abroad.

СПИСОК ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ:

1. Аблязова, О., Бадалова, Ж., & Ибрагимова, Г. (2019). Проблемы преподавания иностранных языков студентам экономических специальностей. Вестник университета Караганды, 4(96), 143-148.
2. Мамадалиева, М. (2016). Особенности преподавания английского языка для студентов экономических специальностей. Научно-технический журнал "Логос", 2(91), 59-64.
3. Мирзаева, Н., & Камалова, Я. (2019). Использование инновационных методов при обучении английскому языку студентов-экономистов. Журнал научных публикаций аспирантов и докторантов, 6(63), 44-48.
4. Сулейманова, З. & Латифова, Н. (2019). Определение эффективности аутентичных материалов в обучении английскому языку студентов экономического факультета. Проблемы современной науки и образования, (3), 126-129.
5. Хуснукрадова, Р. & Абдуллаева, А. (2017). Использование новых технологий в преподавании английского языка для студентов экономических специальностей. Научно-практический журнал "Проблемы развития науки и образования", 1(16), 52-55.
6. Al-Mohammadi, A. M. (2018). The impact of utilizing authentic materials on enhancing EFL learners' reading comprehension skill. International Education and Research Journal, 4(5), 36-38.
7. Al-Mekhlafi, A. G., & Al-Zubaidi, S. M. (2016). Challenges of teaching English language to Arab students. International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Research, 6(1), 29-36.
8. Bennui, P., & Henning, M. A. (2016). Innovative approach to developing business English programs: Blended learning and multiprofessional collaboration. English for Specific Purposes World, 51, 1-13.
9. Chen, C. (2018). The implementation of task-based language teaching in EFL writing classes: Innovation and challenges. Theory and Practice in Language Studies, 8(8), 1007-1018.

10. Yilmaz, H. (2019). The impact of extensive reading on Iranian English language learners' speakingability. E-Journal of New World Sciences Academy, 14(1), 514-524.